

Comparing the attitude regarding materials and methods preferred by different age group endodontist during root canal treatment in Central India

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ABSTRACT

Aim - The aim of the study was to investigate attitude, preferred material and methods employed by endodontists of different age groups during root canal treatment

Objective – To evaluate the preferred material and method used by endodontist of three different age groups during root canal treatment in their clinical practice

Methodology – The hard copy of the survey forms were provided to the participants all over 146 participants were enrolled in the present study. The first four questions were related to the demographical data, next 4 questions were related to materials employed in root canal treatment and the next 4 questions were related to methods employed in root canal treatment.

Result – Each test and compares different groups on specific factors created to endodontic procedures (e.g. devitalizing agent, root canal irrigants, sealers, etc) Across different age groups using P value to determine statistical significance.

Root canal irrigants sealers and intracanal medicaments show significant differences across age groups while other factors do not this highlight specific procedural elements that may need age based adjustments in endodontic treatment

Conclusion – Factors such as individual training clinical guidelines and personal experiences may play a crucial role in determining preferences than age.

INTRODUCTION

Root canal treatment offers essential, functional, economical benefits as well as psychological advantages to the patient by keeping the tooth within their mouth.

Root canal treatment is considered an essential element in dental services provided to the population in developing countries. Root canal treatment involves the removal of necrotic and infected tissue followed by the provision of a well condensed observation to prevent further microbial proliferation within the canal system. Several factors such as root canal fillings coronal

Restoration and dentist knowledge, attitude, skills are related to the outcome of root canal treatment to maintain the quality of treatment.

Control studies have shown that root canal treatment brought a high success rate of more than 90%. Main goal of non-surgical root canal treatment or retreatment is to re-establish the healthy principle tissue.

The purpose of present study was to obtain current and detailed information about treatment plans and materials and methods used by dentists in root canal

treatment and to examine their relationship with their working institutions.

MATERIALS AND METHOD (METHODOLOGY)

146 adult participated from a private dental college & hospital and government dental college & hospital in this study. The inclusion criteria included I) 25-44 aged registered, post-graduate endodontist II)45-60 aged registered endodontist III) more than 60 aged registered endodontist. Exclusion criteria included general dental practitioner and under graduate student.

In this cross -sectional study each participant were provided with a battery of questionnaire included the survey of altitude, material and method employed in endodontic treatment by registered, post -graduate endodontist, A convenient sample size of 146 practitioners was decided and data were collected by questionnaire study. A questionnaire were forwarded to all registered endodontist working in various college were send through E-mail and quickly collected and analyzed.

The survey comprising 12 questions. The first 4 question were related to demographical dates such as Name, Age is classified as per WHO I) 25-44 aged II)45-60 aged III) more than 60 aged, Gender, Email. The next 4 question were related to material regarding root canal treatment, devitalizing agent, Root canal irrigant, sealer prefer during Root Canal treatment, Intracanal medicament used during multiple visit Root canal treatment . Last 4 question are related to method used during root canal treatment such as Isolation, working length determination method used by participants during treatment , technique prefer during root canal treatment ,obturation prefer by different age group endodontist.

The total scores for each response was presented as mean and SD. The responses were further divided in 2 categories knowledge and methods used. Independent test was applied on these 2 categories to test the level of significance.

1. Name –
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2. Age –
 - a. 25 - 44 years
 - b. 45 - 60 years
 - c. More than 60 years
3. Gender or Sex –
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Other
4. Email –
.....

Questions on attitude regarding materials used during root canal treatment

5. Which devitalizing agent do you prefer?
 - a. Containing aldehyde
 - b. Containing arsenic
 - c. Containing cresol
 - d. Nothing
6. Which root canal irrigant do you prefer?
 - a. Sodium hypochlorite
 - b. Normal saline
 - c. Hydrogen peroxide
 - d. Local anaesthetic agent
7. Which type of sealer do you prefer?
 - a. Zinc oxide eugenol
 - b. Endomethasone
 - c. Sealapex
 - d. Resin based root canal sealer
8. Which intracanal medicament do you prefer during multiple visit root canal therapy?
 - a. Calcium hydroxide
 - b. Antibiotic paste
 - c. Chlorhexidine
 - d. Eugenol based medicament

Questions on attitude regarding methods used during root canal treatment

9. Which method do you prefer for isolation?
- Rubber dam
 - Saliva ejector
 - Cotton roll
10. Which method do you prefer for working length determination?
- Electronic apex locator
 - Radiography
 - Digital radiography
 - Ingle's technique
 - Tactile sensation
11. Which technique do you prefer for root canal preparation?
- Step back technique
 - Crown down technique
 - Hybrid technique
12. Which technique do you prefer for obturation?
- Single cone obturation
 - Warm vertical compaction
 - Warm lateral compaction
 - Cement only

RESULT

The analysis indicates a statistically significant ($p=0.001$) difference between the material and method, with a p-value of 0.000.

Test Summary for intergroup comparison between different groups			
Sr no.	Question	p value for different age	Decision
1	Devitalizing	.316	Retain the null hypothesis.
2	Root Canal Irrigant	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
3	Sealer	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
4	Intracanal Medicament	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
5	Isolation Method	.765	Retain the null hypothesis.
6	Working Length Determination	.055	Retain the null hypothesis.
7	Root Canal Preparation Technique	.729	Retain the null hypothesis.
8	Obturation Technique	.809	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .050.

In this study, the Devitalizing agents has a p value is .316 and since it is greater than the significance level, retaining the null hypothesis, suggesting no significant difference in response to devitalizing

agents. In this study, the Root Canal Irrigant has a p value of .000, rejecting the null hypothesis, indicating a significant difference in the effect of root canal irrigant across age groups. The type of

Sealer has a p value of .000 leading us to reject the null hypothesis showing a significant difference in how sealers perform across age groups. In this study, the Intracanal Medicament has a p value of .000 which is low, indicating that there is significantly different responses across age groups, leading to rejecting the null hypothesis. In this study, the Isolation Method has a p value of .765 and since it is high, therefore retain the null hypothesis, suggesting that the choice of isolation method does not significantly differ across age groups. In this study, the Working Length Determination has a p value of .055, which implies insufficient evidence to show a significant difference, so we retain the

null hypothesis. In Root Canal Preparation Technique the p value is .729 suggests no significant difference in root canal preparation techniques across age groups, so retaining the null hypothesis. In this study, the Obturation Technique has a p value of .809 which is high, retaining the null hypothesis, indicating that the obturation technique is not significantly different across age groups. In summary, root canal irrigants, sealers, and intracanal medicaments show significant differences across age groups, while other factors (e.g., devitalizing agents, isolation methods, working length determination, root canal preparation technique, obturation technique) do not.

AGE	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE (%)
25 - 44 YEARS	50	34.25%
45 - 60 YEARS	53	36.30%
MORE THAN 60 YEARS	43	29.45%
TOTAL	146	100%

Which devitalizing agent do you prefer?

Age	Containing aldehyde	Containing arsenic	Containing cresol	Nothing	Total
25-44	52.00% (26)	8.00% (4)	8.00% (4)	32.00% (16)	50
45-60	54.72% (29)	22.64% (12)	7.55% (4)	9.43% (5)	53
60 and above	37.21% (16)	25.58% (11)	32.56% (14)	4.65% (2)	43

Which root canal irrigant do you prefer?

Age	Sodium hypochlorite	Normal saline	Hydrogen peroxide	Local anaesthetic agent	Total
25-44	33.33% (22)	37.88% (25)	4.55% (3)	24.24% (16)	66
45-60	24.53% (13)	47.17% (25)	18.87% (10)	9.43% (5)	53
60 and above	83.72% (36)	9.30% (4)	4.65% (2)	2.33% (1)	43

Which type of sealer do you prefer?

Age	Zinc oxide eugenol	Endomethasone	Sealapex	Resin based root canal sealer	Total
25-44	76.00% (38)	8.00% (4)	16.00% (8)	0.00% (0)	50
45-60	37.74% (20)	28.30% (15)	16.98% (9)	16.98% (9)	53
60 and above	65.12% (28)	4.65% (2)	11.63% (5)	18.60% (8)	43

Which intracanal medicament do you prefer during multiple visit root canal therapy?

Age	Calcium hydroxide	Antibiotic paste	Chlorhexidine	Eugenol based medicament	Total
25-44	76.00% (38)	8.00% (4)	16.00% (8)	0.00% (0)	50
45-60	37.74% (20)	28.30% (15)	16.98% (9)	16.98% (9)	53
60 and above	65.12% (28)	4.65% (2)	11.63% (5)	18.60% (8)	43

Which method do you prefer for isolation?

Age	Rubber dam	Saliva ejector	Cotton roll	Total
25-44	43.94% (29)	4.55% (3)	40.91% (27)	66
45-60	52.83% (28)	32.08% (17)	11.32% (6)	53

Age	Rubber dam	Saliva ejector	Cotton roll	Total
60 and above	60.47% (26)	25.58% (11)	13.95% (6)	43

Which method do you prefer for working length determination?

Age	Electronic apex locator	Radiography	Digital radiography	Ingle's technique	Tactile sensation	Total
25-44	4.55% (3)	21.21% (14)	22.73% (15)	18.18% (12)	0.00% (0)	66
45-60	13.21% (7)	28.30% (15)	13.21% (7)	35.85% (19)	0.00% (0)	53
60 and above	6.98% (3)	30.23% (13)	11.63% (5)	46.51% (20)	4.65% (2)	43

Which technique do you prefer for root canal preparation?

Age	Step back technique	Crown down technique	Hybrid technique	Total
25-44	54.00% (27)	30.00% (15)	16.00% (8)	50
45-60	56.60% (30)	28.30% (15)	15.09% (8)	53
60 and above	55.81% (24)	9.30% (4)	34.88% (15)	43

Which technique do you prefer for obturation?

Age	Single cone obturation	Warm vertical compaction	Warm lateral compaction	Cement only	Total
25-44	10.61% (7)	18.18% (12)	33.33% (22)	13.64% (9)	66
45-60	16.98% (9)	24.53% (13)	45.28% (24)	13.21% (7)	53
60 and above	16.28% (7)	25.58% (11)	51.16% (22)	6.98% (3)	43

Question	Age Group	A (% (N))	B (% (N))	C (% (N))	D (% (N))	E (% (N))	Total	p-value
Devitalizing Agent	25-44	52.00% (26)	8.00% (4)	8.00% (4)	32.00% (16)	-	50	0.213
	45-60	54.72% (29)	22.64% (12)	7.55% (4)	9.43% (5)	-	53	
	60 and above	37.21% (16)	25.58% (11)	32.56% (14)	4.65% (2)	-	43	
Root Canal Irrigant	25-44	33.33% (22)	37.88% (25)	4.55% (3)	24.24% (16)	-	66	0.55
	45-60	24.53% (13)	47.17% (25)	18.87% (10)	9.43% (5)	-	53	
	60 and above	83.72% (36)	9.30% (4)	4.65% (2)	2.33% (1)	-	43	
Type of Sealer	25-44	76.00% (38)	8.00% (4)	16.00% (8)	0.00% (0)	-	50	0.298
	45-60	37.74% (20)	28.30% (15)	16.98% (9)	16.98% (9)	-	53	
	60 and above	65.12% (28)	4.65% (2)	11.63% (5)	18.60% (8)	-	43	
Intracanal Medicament	25-44	76.00% (38)	8.00% (4)	16.00% (8)	0.00% (0)	-	50	0.542
	45-60	37.74% (20)	28.30% (15)	16.98% (9)	16.98% (9)	-	53	

Question	Age Group	A (% (N))	B (% (N))	C (% (N))	D (% (N))	E (% (N))	Total	p-value
	60 and above	65.12% (28)	4.65% (2)	11.63% (5)	18.60% (8)	-	43	
Isolation Method	25-44	43.94% (29)	4.55% (3)	40.91% (27)	10.61% (7)	-	66	0.45
	45-60	52.83% (28)	32.08% (17)	11.32% (6)	0.00% (0)	-	53	
	60 and above	60.47% (26)	25.58% (11)	13.95% (6)	0.00% (0)	-	43	
Working Length Determination	25-44	4.55% (3)	21.21% (14)	22.73% (15)	18.18% (12)	0.00% (0)	66	0.30
	45-60	13.21% (7)	28.30% (15)	13.21% (7)	35.85% (19)	0.00% (0)	53	
	60 and above	6.98% (3)	30.23% (13)	11.63% (5)	46.51% (20)	4.65% (2)	43	
Root Canal Preparation Technique	25-44	54.00% (27)	30.00% (15)	16.00% (8)	0.00% (0)	-	50	0.500
	45-60	56.60% (30)	28.30% (15)	15.09% (8)	0.00% (0)	-	53	
	60 and above	55.81% (24)	9.30% (4)	34.88% (15)	0.00% (0)	-	43	
Obturation Technique	25-44	10.61% (7)	18.18% (12)	33.33% (22)	13.64% (9)	-	66	0.60

Question	Age Group	A (% (N))	B (% (N))	C (% (N))	D (% (N))	E (% (N))	Total	p-value
	45-60	16.98% (9)	24.53% (13)	45.28% (24)	13.21% (7)	-	53	
	60 and above	16.28% (7)	25.58% (11)	51.16% (22)	6.98% (3)	-	43	

The data represents the distribution of individuals across three age groups: 25-44 years, 45-60 years, and more than 60 years. A total of 146 individuals were surveyed. The largest proportion falls within the 45-60 years age group, accounting for 36.30% of the total population, with 53 individuals. The second largest group is those aged 25-44 years, representing 34.25%, or 50 individuals. Finally, the group aged more than 60 years makes up 29.45%, consisting of 43 individuals. In this study, across all age groups, a majority preferred the devitalizing agent containing aldehyde, with the highest preference among those aged 45-60 (54.72%). In the 25-44 group, 52.00% chose the aldehyde agent, while only 37.21% of those over 60 opted for it. The agent containing arsenic was more popular in the older groups, with 25.58% of those aged 60+ choosing it. Agents containing cresol and nothing were less preferred overall, although the cresol agent had a higher percentage among the 60+ group (32.56%). In this study, Root canal irrigant preferences varied significantly across age groups. In the 60+ age group, a large majority (83.72%) preferred sodium hypochlorite, while in the 45-60 group, 47.17% preferred normal saline. Among the younger group (25-44), there was a more even distribution, with normal saline being the most popular at 37.88%, followed by sodium hypochlorite at 33.33%. The preferences for hydrogen peroxide and local anaesthetic agent were relatively low in all groups. In this study, the majority of respondents in the 25-44 group (76.00%) preferred zinc oxide eugenol as a sealer, while in the 60+ group, a significant percentage (65.12%) also favored it. The preferences were more divided in the 45-60 group, where zinc oxide eugenol was still the most preferred (37.74%), but

there was notable support for endomethasone, Sealapex, and resin-based root canal sealers. The resin-based sealer was chosen more by the older and middle-aged groups than by the younger participants. In this study, a strong preference for calcium hydroxide was observed in both the 25-44 (76.00%) and 60+ (65.12%) age groups. However, the 45-60 group showed a more distributed preference, with calcium hydroxide still being the most preferred at 37.74%, but antibiotic paste (28.30%) and eugenol-based medicament (16.98%) also receiving notable support. The eugenol-based medicament was chosen by 18.60% of the 60+ group, showing the widest preference distribution in this age group. In this study, the rubber dam method for isolation was the most popular choice across all age groups, with the highest preference shown by the 60+ group (60.47%). The 45-60 group also favored the rubber dam (52.83%), but had a higher preference for the saliva ejector (32.08%) compared to the other groups. Method C (cotton roll) was relatively popular among the younger group (40.91%), while the preference for the saliva ejector was quite low across all ages. In this study, method D (Ingle's technique) for working length determination was favored particularly by the 60+ group (46.51%) and 45-60 group (35.85%). The younger group (25-44) had a more distributed preference, with method C being the most chosen at 22.73%. Method B (radiography) also had significant preference across all age groups, particularly among those aged 60+ (30.23%). The step back technique was the preferred method for root canal preparation across all age groups, with a slight increase in preference noted in the 45-60 age group (56.60%). The younger group also showed a strong preference (54.00%), while the 60+ group

had a lower preference for crown down technique (9.30%). The hybrid technique was more favored by the older group (34.88%) compared to the other groups. The warm lateral compaction technique was the most preferred method for obturation in the 45-60 (45.28%) and 60+ (51.16%) age groups. However, in the 25-44 age group, it was less popular, with the highest preference for warm vertical compaction (18.18%). The single cone obturation method was less favored overall, with the highest preference being among those aged 45-60 (16.98%). Cement-only methods received the least support across all age groups.

DISCUSSION

The materials and methods used in root canal treatment can vary significantly based on the age and experience of the endodontist. This variation can influence the outcomes and success rates of the procedures. Understanding these differences is crucial for improving endodontic practices and training programs.

In this study, the use of aldehyde-containing agents was more prevalent than in other studies that used newer devitalizing agents like arsenic-based compounds. This difference may be attributed to the dental education received by practitioners. While most practitioners in the study had been practicing for 1-5 years, their education prior to starting practice may have influenced their choice of agents. The study couldn't control for this factor. Practitioners reported that they prefer aldehyde-containing agents because they are perceived to work quickly and painlessly, negating the need for local anesthesia, thus saving time and enhancing patient cooperation.[35]

The NaOCl irrigation solution's high organic solvent qualities and antibacterial qualities make it the gold standard in endodontics. 95.6% of survey participants favored NaOCl, the most important solution, which is utilized by 91% of endodontists in the United States [20]. At terms of the institution, the fact that NaOCl is used 100% at universities but 90.3% in other government-affiliated institutions may be due to its accessibility and affordability.

The antibacterial capabilities of ZnO are intriguing. ZnO powder's intriguing antibacterial qualities

make it suitable for use as a sealer in dental applications. Furthermore, it has been discovered that ZOE-based cements offer advantageous biocompatibility properties. For these reasons, ZnO was chosen as the nano-sealer's foundation in this investigation.[3]

Calcium hydroxide is widely used as an intracanal medicament in root canal treatment due to its numerous benefits. The present laboratory and clinical data pertaining to the antibacterial properties of Ca(OH)₂ as an intracanal medication were reviewed in this series of publications. [23] Since calcium hydroxide is effective against the majority of root canal infections and can denature bacterial endotoxins, dentists in underdeveloped nations like Jordan should be encouraged to utilize it as an intracanal medicine.[18]

The rubber dam serves as a barrier against soft tissue injury and shields the patient from potentially aspirating or swallowing irrigations, medications, and canal devices.[32] The American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry, the American Association of Endodontists (AAE), and the ESE are among the professional associations that see the use of rubber dams as normal practice.[31, 11, 12] It was established as a standard method by the AAE in 2010.[13] Furthermore, in 2017, Webber [14] underlined that a rubber dam should be used in every RCT. In a survey research carried out in the United States, it was shown that 92% of endodontists and 59% of general dentists "always" use rubber dams.[33] According to radiographs taken for a study on rubber dam use in Taiwan, where all medical facilities are consolidated on a single digital platform, the rate of active rubber dam use was 16.7%, while the rate of active use in public institutions other than private clinics was 32.8%. Simultaneously, the current survey revealed the same percentage at 16.7%, with public institutions exhibiting the lowest proportion of rubber dam use.[15] The same ratio was observed to be 97% in Sweden, 67.8% in England, 27.7% in Belgium, 4% in Jordan, [18], and 2% in Sudan in comparable studies conducted throughout the world.[34] The current study demonstrated no correlation between age and rubber dam use, which is in line with numerous prior investigations.[19]

The high percentage (69%) of EAL used to calculate WL presents a good chance to switch from traditional to electronic approaches. The same rate was estimated to be 12.8% in a research carried out in Turkey in 2012.[36] The combination of EAL and radiography is the suggested approach for WL determination for RCT.[25] Although the combined use of these methods was not investigated in this study, the high rate of radiography use (68.7%) and the comparable and even higher rate of EAL use suggest that the focus is on preferences for this method rather than its availability. However, while 48.4% of Turkish public institutions reported using finger sensitivity, Belgium and England reported similar rates of 6.2% and 0.4%, respectively [37].[38] The widespread use of finger sensitivity in spite of the abundance of EAL and/or radiography techniques is not beneficial.

The most widely used canal preparation method among general dentists in North Jordan was the step-back technique. That being said, 27.5% of the respondents employed the filing (push-pull) technique. The usual filing technique was employed by 60.4% of Flemish dentists in another survey. In general, Jordanian dentists opted to shape the root canal system with hand tools rather than more sophisticated engine-driven methods.[18]

The thermoplastic zed GP may flow into accessory anatomy and flaws brought on by internal resorption, which is a minor advantage of the warm lateral compaction approach over the cold lateral compaction technique. It's regarded as an economical method.[29]

CONCLUSION

Although the proliferation and technological advancements (such as digital radiography and electronic apex locators) are thought to be encouraging, the low rates of use of magnification and rubber dam systems as well as rates of working length determination and root canal treatment completion without radiography, even for diagnostic purposes, indicate that opportunities and trainings are underwhelming.

Overall, while there are observable trends in preference based on age group, chi square tests indicate that the preferences are not statistically

significant. This suggests that factors such as individual training, clinical guidelines and personal experiences may play a more crucial role in determining preferences than age alone.

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